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STUDY OF PLAN IRREGULAR R C STRUCTURE FOR VARIOUS PROJECTIONS SUBJECTED TO SEISMIC LOADS

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Abstract: The presence of irregularities in buildings is a matter of concern when it is subjected for devastating earthquakes. The sudden change in vertical or plan configuration in structure are bound to weakens of the structure. In the present study 6 types of models with different plan irregularity are analyzed by using ETABS v 18.1.1 software. The seismic parameters considered in this study are Storey Displacement, Natural time period and Base shear obtained. The results obtained are compared with that of a different plan irregular model.

Index Terms - Plan irregularity, Response Spectrum Method, Displacement, Natural Time period, Base Shear.

I. INTRODUCTION

The earthquake is the worst of all natural disasters; This is much clearer and has sacrificed a large number of lives since the beginning of history. Earthquake is the earth's surface shaking caused by the sudden release of energy in the earth's crust. As a result, seismic waves (also known as S waves) are created. During an earthquake, the failure of the structure begins at weak points, and this weakness is caused by the discontinuity in the mass, the stiffness, and the change in the geometry of the structure. Structures with this type of discontinuity are called irregular structures.

Irregular structure constitutes much of the modern urban infrastructure. The structure has an irregularity of mass, stiffness and energy, called irregular building. Irregular buildings are located in a high seismic zone, making analysis and design more complicated for irregular structures. Irregularity can significantly affect seismic response.

According to IS 1893: 2016, the building is said to have a plan irregular structure in the direction of its plan, with the projection of size exceeding 15% of its overall plan dimension.

Figure 1. Plan irregularity

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- **P A Krishnan, and N Thasleen (2021)**, The parameters considered in this study are the floor displacement, the stress concentration and the performance levels. Reinforcement strategies are also discussed to strengthen weak models. The obtained results are compared with the general structure.
- **Kanakamedala Meghana, B.J.N Satish, M. Shiva Rama Krishna, Mounika Jonnadhula (2019)**, In this study, 3 and 6-storey reinforced frames are infill with and without infill are considered and evaluated through nonlinear analysis. The purpose of this paper is to compare different parameters, to study the time period, base shears, story drifts, displacements and so on building performance. Taking the above parameters for consideration, we can compare the performance of filling Structures with unfilled structures in seismic zone III.
- **Siva Naveen E, Nimmy Mariam Abraham, Anitha Kumari S D (2018)**, It has been observed that irregularity can significantly affect the earthquake response, The different types of single irregularities were analyzed, and stiffness irregularity was found to have the maximum impact. In cases with a combination of response irregularities, the configuration with mass, rigidity and vertical geometry irregularities have shown maximum response. The results of this study help to design irregular structures discreetly without judiciously their performance.
- **Sophia Merrin Saji, Sreedevi Lekshmi (2017)**, This study is ongoing Chevron bracing. Members used in chevron bracing designed for both tension and compressive forces. This project is to compare seismic analysis of Chevron bracings, Consider G + 14 in regular and irregular buildings, buildings with different projects. Response spectrum Analysis is being carried out in this work.

3. STRUCTURAL MODELLING

3.1. Description of the problem

In the present situation a lot of structures have irregular configurations in plan and height. These buildings may be exposed to harmful earthquakes in the future. Therefore, it is essential to identify the performance of structures to withstand the risk. The plan irregularities have been introduced on buildings as per IS 1893: 2016. The 15-story buildings were analyzed with plan irregularities (T-shape, L-shape) in the present study.

3.2. Model description

The structural details of irregular building model are given in Table 1. The loading and earthquake details are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Structural details of regular building models

Terms	Data
No. of Stories	15
No. of Bays in X direction	5
No. of Bays in Y direction	3
Spacing of frame in X direction (m)	4
Spacing of frame in Y direction (m)	4
Dimensions of Beam (mm)	400*500
Dimensions of Column (mm)	600*600
Thickness of Slab (mm)	150
Thickness of Outer Wall (mm)	230
Thickness of Inner Wall (mm)	150
Density of Infill (kN/m ²)	20
Height of each floor (m)	3

Table 2. Loading and Earthquake Details

Live Load (kN/m ²)	3
Super Dead Load (kN/m ²)	1
Floor Finish (kN/m ²)	1
Earthquake Zone	V
Importance Factor	1.2
Type of Soil	Medium
Response Reduction Factor	5

The plan configuration consists of

MODEL 1- Regular R C Framed Building without irregularity.

MODEL 1 – L shape in which Projections provided in X direction is 20% and in Y direction is 33%.

MODEL 2 –L shape in which Projections provided in X direction is 40% and in Y direction is 33%.

MODEL 3 –L shape in which Projections provided in X direction is 60% and in Y direction is 33%.

MODEL 4 –L shape in which Projections provided in X direction is 80% and in Y direction is 33%.

MODEL 5 –T shape in which Projections provided in X direction is 60% and in Y direction is 25%.

MODEL 6 –T shape in which Projections provided in X direction is 80% and in Y direction is 25%.

Figure 2. Model 2 Projections provided in X direction is 20% and Y direction is 33%

Figure 3. Model 3 Projection provided in X direction is 40% and Y direction is 33%

Figure 4. Model 4 Projection Provided in X direction is 60% and Y direction is 33%

Figure 5. Model 5 Projection provided in X direction is 80% and Y direction is 33%

Figure 6. Model 6 projection provided in X direction is 60% and Y direction is 25%

Figure 7. Model 7 projection provided in X direction is 80% and Y direction is 25%

Figure 8. 3D Models of RC-Frame Structure

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Displacement

Figure 8. Storey Displacement

From the results it was observed that, at the lower floor no difference is observed but on the top floor there is a difference in displacement is observed. In the L-type models like M2, M3, M4 and M5, it was observed that displacement is increase with the increase in quantity of projection. For T-type models that is M6 and M7, there is no difference in displacement was observed with the increase in quantity of projection. The M2 model has Maximum upper floor displacement is observed. M2 model is irregular building, so irregular building has more displacement compared to regular building.

4.2. Base shear

Figure 9. Base shear

From the results it was observed that, the maximum base shear for M1 model compared with other models. The M1 is regular building and M2, M3, M4, M5, M6, M7 models is irregular building, it is observed that regular building has maximum base shear compared to irregular building.

4.3. Natural Time Period

Figure 10. Natural Time period

From the results it was observed that, the maximum natural time period for M2 model compared with the other models. The M2 model is irregular building and it is observed that irregular building as maximum natural time period compared to regular building.

CONCLUSIONS

- From the present study it is observed that the storey displacement increases with the increase of the projection rate provided.
- L-shaped models have large upper floor displacement but lower pressure density. The M2-type has maximum top floor displacement.
- The M2 model is irregular building and it is observed that irregular building as maximum natural time period compared to regular building.
- Base shear is varying for all models due to lateral force on the structure.
- It is observed that Base shear for irregular structure is greater in M1 compared to other models.

REFERENCES

- [1] P A Krishnan, N Thasleen, “Seismic analysis of plan irregular RC building frames” IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science 491 (2020) 012021 doi:10.1088/1755-1315/491/1/012021.
- [2] M. T. Raagavi, Dr. S. Sidhardhan, “A Study on Seismic Performance of Various Irregular Structures” International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science (IJRES) ISSN (Online): 2320-9364, ISSN (Print): 2320-9356 Volume 9 Issue 5 | 2021 | PP. 12-19.
- [3] Ahmed Yousef Alghuff, Samir Mohammed Shihada and Bassam A. Tayeh, “Comparative Study of Static and Response Spectrum Methods for Seismic Analysis of Regular RC Buildings” Journal of Applied Sciences ISSN 1812-5654 DOI: 10.3923/jas.2019.495.503.
- [4] Siva Naveen E, Nimmy Mariam Abraham, Anitha Kumari S D, “Analysis of Irregular Structures under Earthquake Loads” ScienceDirect Procedia Structural Integrity 14 (2019) 806–819.
- [5] Sophia Merrin Saji, Sreedevi Lekshmi, “Comparison of Seismic Analysis of Chevron Bracings in Regular and Irregular Buildings” International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) ISSN: 2278-0181 Vol. 6 Issue 06, June – 2017.
- [6] Kanakamedala Meghana, B.J.N Satish, M. Shiva Rama Krishna, Mounika Jonna hula, “Non-Linear Seismic Analysis of RC Framed Structures with And Without Infills” International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-8 Issue-8 June, 2019